

Determination of dry biomass, relative water content, malondialdehyde, and hydrogen peroxide content in Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) infected with nematodes

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Among the top five plant pathogens known for adversely affecting plant productivity, root-knot nematodes hold a prominent position as destructive parasites of vegetable plants. As part of a phytopathological survey initiative conducted in the Ganja-Gazakh economic region, samples displaying typical symptoms of nematode infestation were collected from potato plants. Microscopic examination revealed a high prevalence of *Meloidogyne* spp., a genus of nematodes, in the Tovuz region (76.8%), whereas a lower prevalence was observed in the Aghstafa region (22.2%). Concurrently, an analysis was conducted on the leaves of both healthy plants and those infected with nematodes, focusing on dry biomass, relative water content, hydrogen peroxide, and malondialdehyde. The results indicated that nematode infection leads to an increase in malondialdehyde and hydrogen peroxide levels, while simultaneously causing a decrease in dry biomass and relative water content in the potato plants.

Keywords: *Solanum tuberosum* L., *Meloidogyne* spp., root-knot nematodes, hydrogen peroxide, malondialdehyde

INTRODUCTION

Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) production holds great significance in the agricultural sector of Azerbaijan. As per the UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) data from 2020, Azerbaijan achieved a potato production of approximately 734,000 tons, securing its position among the top 32 countries worldwide in potato cultivation. The Ganja-Kazakh economic region, encompassing areas like Aghstafa, Dashkasan, Gadabay, Goranboy, and Tovuz is primarily responsible for potato cultivation due to its favorable soil and climatic conditions. Potatoes serve not only as a staple food but also as a valuable source of starch and animal feed. However, potato productivity faces challenges from dangerous pests, with nematode-induced diseases playing a significant role in impacting yields. Scientists have identified over 50 nematode species that pose serious threats to potato plants (Yu et al., 2012). Among the most destructive species are the golden potato cyst nematode (*Globodera rostochiensis*) and the white potato cyst nematode (*Globodera pallida*),

acknowledged as quarantine pests in numerous countries due to their potential to cause substantial economic losses in potato crops (Madani et al., 2005). Plant-parasitic root-knot nematodes, commonly known as *Meloidogyne* spp., are microscopic roundworms that pose significant risks to various crops, including potatoes. Infected plants exhibit symptoms such as chlorosis, yellowness, and leaf twisting in the upper sections (Mammadhasanova et al., 2021). Severe infections lead to the development of necrotic spots on leaves and stem, often resulting in plant destruction. *Meloidogyne* spp. nematodes primarily infect potato roots globally, leading to biochemical alterations in the plant that can impede growth, reduce yield, and affect the quality (Khan et al., 2014). The transmission of *Meloidogyne* nematodes to potato plants can occur through contaminated soil or infected plants, including tools and equipment carrying the nematodes (Liang et al., 2001). Upon infecting the potato plant, these nematodes induce the formation of characteristic tumors or nodules on the roots. This weakens the plant's capacity to absorb water and nutrients,

resulting in decreased growth and yield. Crop rotation, utilization of resistant potato cultivars, and soil fumigation represent common control measures used to manage *Meloidogyne* infestations in potato fields (Griffin et al., 1996). However, the disease's progression varies depending on the plant's growth cycle and is characterized by various biochemical and physiological changes.

Moreover, plants possess physiological and biochemical indicators that determine their resistance to pathogens of diverse natures. These indicators are responsible for alterations in plant metabolism and vitality during stressful situations. Biotic stress factors, for instance, trigger the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) within cells, leading to oxidative stress (Desaeger and Rao, 2000). Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) is a molecule widely present in various biological systems, serving as a crucial component. It is enzymatically produced within living cells during oxidation reactions and as a result of electron leakage from electron transport chains. Additionally, H_2O_2 functions as a signaling molecule, regulating plant development, stress adaptation, and programmed cell death (PCD) (Apel and Hirt, 2004).

Malondialdehyde (MDA) is a product generated during lipid peroxidation, with its synthesis increasing under stress conditions caused by the accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in plant cells due to pathogen infection. MDA is used as a marker to assess oxidative stress in plants, and its buildup indicates ROS-induced cell damage. In certain cases, MDA can directly contribute to cell damage by interacting with other cellular components like proteins and DNA. Hence, MDA acts as an indicator of plant disease susceptibility and can potentially influence the development of plant diseases.

Considering the aforementioned aspects, the primary objective of this study was to determine the impact of *Meloidogyne* nematodes on potato plants by assessing changes in dry biomass, relative water content, as well as levels of malondialdehyde and hydrogen peroxide. These physiological changes are considered fundamental indicators of nematode-induced alterations in potato plants.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study object: Potato plant (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) leaves, both healthy and infected with *Meloidogyne* spp. nematodes were collected from various locations (Gadabay, Samukh, Shamkir, Aghstafa, Dashkasan, Goranboy, and Tovuz) in the Ganja-Kazakh economic region of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Soil samples were collected following the Prot and Ferris method (1992).

Microscopic diagnosis: Phytopathological examinations were conducted to identify characteristic symptoms of nematode infection in the collected plant samples. The Berman method was used to extract potato nematodes from soil and plant material. This involved using a rubber tube with a length of 10-15 cm, an iron grid with small holes, and a glass funnel attached to a tripod. Hot water at a temperature of 36°-38°C was poured onto the mold, and a portion of the soil or root sample was placed on the grid and left for 1-2 hours. Nematodes in the sediment were initially observed using a light microscope. The differentiation of adult male and female nematodes, as well as the morphology and features of various perineal regions, were studied using a JEOL "JCM-6000" SEM3 scanning electron microscope. Permanent slide preparations of the identified nematodes were made following the methodology of Seessao et al. (2017).

Measurement of malondialdehyde (MDA) levels: To investigate the intensity of lipid peroxidation, the amount of malondialdehyde (MDA) in healthy and nematode-infected potato leaves was determined spectrophotometrically. The MDA content was measured at 523 nm and 600 nm wavelengths using the reaction with thiobarbituric acid. A 0.3 g leaf sample was crushed in 2 ml of 0.1% trichloroacetic acid, followed by centrifugation at 1000g for 10 minutes. The supernatant was mixed with a 0.5% solution of thiobarbituric acid in 20% trichloroacetic acid and heated in a boiling water bath for 30 minutes. After cooling in ice water, the homogenate was centrifuged at 1000g for 15 minutes. The amount of MDA was determined spectrophotometrically using the thiobarbituric acid reaction at 532 nm and 600 nm wavelengths (Heath and Packer, 1968).

Measurement of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) levels: The amount of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) was determined spectrophotometrically following the Bellikampi et al., 2000 method. This method is based on the oxidation of Fe+2 ions to Fe+3 ions by H_2O_2 . Plant material (3 g) was crushed in liquid nitrogen, and 1.5 ml of acetone was added to the homogenate, followed by centrifugation at maximum speed for 10 minutes. To 500 μ l of the supernatant, an equal volume of xylene-orange was added and incubated at room temperature for 40-45 minutes. The absorbance was measured at a wavelength of 560 nm using a spectrophotometer (ULTROSPEC 3300 PRO "Amersham", USA). The amount of H_2O_2 was calculated using the formula:

$$C = ((K \cdot V) / (m \cdot \Delta m)) / 880,$$

where: C represents the amount of H_2O_2 (μ mol/g), K is the amount of H_2O_2 determined from the calibration curve (ng/ml), V is the total volume of the extract (ml), m is the wet weight (g), Δm is the

wet weight ratio to dry biomass, and 880 is a constant factor.

Determination of dry biomass: To measure the dry biomass of potato plant leaves, sections of equal size were taken from both infected and healthy leaf samples, and their mass was determined using an electronic scale. The prepared leaf samples were then placed in a thermostat at 80°C for 24 hours to dry, and the dry weight of the leaves was subsequently determined. The following formula was used to calculate the dry biomass:

$$C = (m_2/m_1) \times 100\%,$$

where: C represents the expression of dry matter content as a percentage by mass, m_1 is the weight of the sample before drying, and m_2 is the weight of the sample after drying.

Determination of relative water content (RWC): RWC in nematode-infected plant samples was determined following the methodology of Tambussi et al. (2005). Initially, a 7-10 cm² section was cut from the central part of each infected and healthy leaf sample to determine the initial weight. The samples were then placed in Petri dishes at a cool temperature for 24 hours, allowing them to be saturated with distilled water without freezing. After measuring the water-saturated weight of the leaves, they were dried in a thermostat at 80°C for 24 hours to determine the dry weight. RWC was calculated using the formula:

$$RWC = 100\% \times (Mf-Md)/(Mt-Md),$$

where: Mf represents the initial weight, Mt is the weight when saturated with water (wet weight), and Md is the dry weight.

Statistical analyses: To assess the significance of variations between the control and experimental groups, a two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used. Significance was attributed to differences in means if the P-value was found to be less than 0.05. Each treatment involved the collection of three separate samples, which were subsequently analyzed twice.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research work aimed to conduct non-periodic phytopathological examinations in potato fields across seven regions (Gadabay, Samukh, Aghstafa, Dashkasan, Goranboy, and Tovuz) of the Ganja-Gazakh economic district, a significant potato production center in the country, between 2019 and 2022. During the study, potential symptoms such as leaf roughness, inward leaf curling, yellowing, and wilting of plants were observed on the diseased plants (Fig.1). Soil samples were collected at a depth of 0-35 cm, considering factors like seasonal characteristics, root depth, soil temperature, and irrigation systems. A total of 58 soil and plant samples were collected, with soil sampling performed at a minimum of 10 locations covering approximately 2 hectares per plot. Additionally, symptomless plants were selected as negative health controls and included in the sampling process. The samples were labeled with field location, date, owner's name, plant type, and plant developmental stage, and then stored in a refrigerator at +4°C. In addition to that, 3-5 soil samples were taken from areas with weeds, and the roots of these weeds were examined for the presence of root galls. Root galls were differentiated from root nodules by tactile examination.

In the laboratory, the collected plant samples (root galls) were dissected to examine the presence of female root-knot nematodes under a microscope. The results were recorded in a table containing the plant name, sample number, and location. Infected samples were marked with a "+" sign, while non-infected samples were marked with a "-" sign. Traditionally, the observation of female perineal features such as visual aspect, dorsal arch, dorsal stripes, and lateral lines has been crucial for identifying *Meloidogyne* nematodes.

Fig. 1. Characteristic symptoms are observed in potato samples infected with nematodes.

Head shape and style morphology in males are key morphometric features used to identify certain *Meloidogyne* species like *M. incognita*, *M. enterolobii*, *M. paraenesis*, and *M. javanica* (Lamberti et al., 2001). For example, the distinctive head morphology of male *M. paranaensis* enables its identification. In diagnostic assessments, specimens were also examined in the transverse position. The distance from the dorsal esophageal gland orifice (DGO) to the base of the stylet in males was used to differentiate between species such as *M. enterolobii* and *M. incognita*. The size and shape of the stylet provided complementary taxonomic value for identifying *Meloidogyne* species.

The genus *Meloidogyne* consists of over 100 species capable of infecting more than 3000 plant species (Nisa et al., 2021). These nematodes exhibit high diversity and are distributed worldwide, predominantly in tropical and subtropical regions. Root-knot nematodes are sedentary endoparasites that induce the formation of giant cells within plant roots to complete their life cycle, and they feed on these giant cells. Unfortunately, the giant cells formed near the xylem and phloem tubes of the root system hinder the water and nutrient uptake by the plant, resulting in morphological and biochemical changes, abnormal plant growth, nutrient deficiencies, root gall formation, and other deformations (Porazinska et al., 1998). Hence, the determination of dry biomass and relative water capacity, considered key physiological indicators, was performed on infected plant leaves. Biochemical and physiological analyses were conducted on both infected potato plant samples and healthy plants, which served as the control group.

Leaf dry weight is a crucial physiological parameter used to estimate leaf biomass and nutrient content. It is determined by removing all the water from fresh leaves through a drying process. After the drying is complete, the leaves are weighed again to obtain the dry weight. The difference between the fresh weight and dry weight represents the water content of the leaf, which is significant for nutrient analysis and physiological studies. Leaf dry weight provides valuable information about plant biomass allocation, nutrient uptake, water relations, and overall plant health. Environmental conditions, genetic factors, and leaf age can influence leaf dry weight. Therefore, it is essential to consider these factors during experiments or when comparing dry weights to ensure accurate results.

Consequently, plant pathogens cause tissue damage, reduce photosynthetic capacity, and alter

plant metabolism, leading to decreased leaf biomass and lower dry weight compared to healthy leaves. In our study, the dry biomass percentage in nematode-infested samples was approximately 1.2 times lower than in non-infested samples (Table 1). Nematode diseases exhibit specific symptoms such as necrotic spots, chlorosis (yellowing), or wilting of leaves. These symptoms are primarily associated with physiological changes in tissues, resulting in reduced leaf dry weight.

It should be noted that the specific effect of biotic stress on leaf dry weight can vary depending on the plant species, type and severity of the stress, and stage of plant development. Additionally, interactions between biotic and abiotic stresses can also impact leaf dry weight. Therefore, studying leaf dry weight under biotic stress requires careful experimental design and control of these factors to accurately assess the effects of stress on plant physiology and biomass distribution.

RWC is another physiological parameter used to evaluate leaf tissue's water status and moisture level. It provides information about the amount of water available in the leaf relative to its fully hydrated state. RWC serves as an indicator of plant water relations and can be used to assess the impact of various environmental factors, including pathogens, on leaf water capacity. In our studies, RWC in nematode-infected potato samples significantly decreased compared to healthy samples (Table 1). Some researchers attribute the physiological changes in plants due to pathogen effects to the plant's hypersensitive response to stress. Several studies have investigated the effects of nematodes on RWC and leaf dry weight in different plant species. For instance, studies on potato plants infected with root necrosis nematodes (*Pratylenchus penetrans*) found significantly lower RWC and dry weight in infected plants, due to nematode-induced damage. Similar results were observed in studies on okra plants (*Abelmoschus esculentus*) infected with root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne incognita*) and tomato plants infected with the same nematode species (*Meloidogyne incognita*), where RWC and dry weight were lower in nematode-infected plants compared to healthy ones (Zouhar et al., 2017; Rahman et al., 2019; Sasanelli et al., 2016).

Interactions between plants and pathogens can involve lipid peroxidation, which plays a significant role in these processes. When plants are attacked by pathogens such as bacteria, fungi, or nematodes, reactive oxygen species (ROS) are produced as part of the plant's defense response. These ROS can induce lipid peroxidation, leading to an oxidizing effect on plant membranes.

Table 1. Content of MDA, H₂O₂, dry biomass and RWC in potato plant leaves infected with nematodes (*Meloidogyne*). The means \pm standard deviation (SD) were determined from three replicates. The results obtained from the two-way ANOVA analysis were represented as follows: *, **, and *** indicated significance at the 0.05, 0.01, and 0.001 probability levels, respectively. The symbol "ns" was used to indicate that the observed differences were not statistically significant.

Plant samples	MDA (malondialdehyde), $\mu\text{mol/g wet mass}$	H ₂ O ₂ (Hydrogen peroxide), $\mu\text{mol/g wet mass}$	Dry Biomass, (%)	Relative Water Content, (%)
Control (healthy)	1.88 \pm 0.09	0.65 \pm 0.03	38	90
Nematode-infected №1	3.17 \pm 0.16	0.87 \pm 0.04	27	68
Nematode-infected №2	2.78 \pm 0.13	0.82 \pm 0.04	28	70
Nematode-infected №3	2.91 \pm 0.14	0.79 \pm 0.03	30	78
Control/NI №1	***	***	-	-
Control/NI №2	***	**	-	-
Control/NI №3	***	**	-	-
NI №1/ NI №2	*	*	-	-
NI №1/ NI №3	*	*	-	-
NI №2/ NI №3	*	*	-	-

Pathogens employ various mechanisms to trigger lipid peroxidation in plant cells. For instance, some pathogens secrete enzymes called lipases that directly degrade lipids, releasing fatty acids that are susceptible to peroxidation. Additionally, interactions between plant defense molecules and pathogen-derived toxins or elicitors can enhance ROS production, thereby promoting lipid peroxidation.

As a consequence of lipid peroxidation, specific products such as malondialdehyde (MDA) and other reactive aldehydes are generated. These lipid peroxidation products serve as signaling molecules and actively participate in regulating defense responses in plants. They activate defense genes, facilitate the synthesis of antimicrobial compounds, and contribute to localized cell death at the site of pathogen invasion. Essentially, lipid peroxidation occurs as a consequence of oxidative stress induced by pathogens in plants, and an increase in the amount of MDA is a primary indicator of this process. In our experiments, nematode-infected plants exhibited an approximately 1.5-1.7 fold increase in MDA levels compared to healthy plants (Table 1).

However, excessive lipid peroxidation can have detrimental effects on plant cells and tissues, compromising their integrity and function. To counteract this, plants possess antioxidant defense systems that mitigate lipid peroxidation and minimize oxidative damage. Investigating lipid peroxidation in the context of plant-pathogen interactions provides valuable insights into the dynamics of plant defense responses and the strategies employed by pathogens to overcome these defenses. Previous studies have demonstrated an elevation in MDA levels due to nematode-

induced oxidative stress in plants (Sasanelli et al., 2016).

Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), a reactive oxygen species (ROS), is recognized for its pivotal role in plant defense against pathogens. When plants encounter pathogens, H₂O₂ is generated as part of their defense response. Acting as a signaling molecule, H₂O₂ triggers diverse defense mechanisms to combat pathogens. In our study, the amount of H₂O₂ was comparatively analyzed between nematode-infected and healthy samples. It was observed that all nematode-infected samples exhibited a significant increase in H₂O₂ levels compared to healthy plants (Table 1). Pathogens, including nematodes, fungi, and viruses, induce H₂O₂ synthesis in plant cells through the recognition of pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) or interaction between plant defense proteins and pathogen effectors. This recognition activates enzymes known as respiratory burst oxidase homologs (RBOHs) or NADPH oxidases, which catalyze the reduction of molecular oxygen to generate H₂O₂. Subsequently, H₂O₂ acts as a signaling molecule, initiating a process known as oxidative stress.

Study of lipid peroxidation, H₂O₂ production, signaling, and plant-pathogen interactions can contribute to the development of effective disease management strategies in agriculture.

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Nematodlarla yoluxmuş kartof (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) bitkisinə quru biokütlənin, nisbi su tutumunun, malondialdehidinin və hidrogen-peroksidin miqdarının təyini

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Kök-düyün nematodları tərəvəz bitkilərinin məhsuldarlığına təsir göstərən təhlükəli ilk beş bitki patogenləri arasında yer almaqdadır. Gəncə-Qazax iqtisadi rayonu ərazisinə təşkil edilən fitopatoloji müayinələr zamanı kartof bitkisindən xarakterik nematod əlamətlərinə malik nümunələr toplanılmışdır. *Meloidogyne* spp. cinsinə məxsus nematodlar mikroskopik üsullardan istifadə etməklə Tovuz rayonunda yüksək ekstensivliklə (76,8%), Ağstafa rayonunda isə aşağı ekstensivliklə (22,2%) aşkar edilmişdir. Eyni zamanda sağlam və nematodla yoluxmuş kartof bitkisinin yarpaqlarında quru biokütlənin, nisbi su tutumunun, hidrogen-peroksidin və malondialdehidinin miqdarı tədqiq edilmişdir. Müəyyən edilmişdir ki, bitkinin nematodlarla yoluxması malondialdehidinin və hidrogen-peroksidin miqdarının artmasına, quru biokütlənin və nisbi su tutumunun isə azalmasına səbəb olur.

Açar sözlər: *Solanum tuberosum* L., *Meloidogyne* spp., kök-düyün nematodları, hidrogen-peroksid, malondialdehid